

Irreducible dynamics in reaction systems*

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The subject of the dynamics of reaction systems (RSs) has been of interest in recent years [3, 5]. A problem already well understood is deciding if there exists a global attractor cycle in the dynamics of an RS [1, 3]. This problem can be equivalently stated as asking if its dynamics forms a connected graph or, on the contrary, if it is the *alternative* execution of two disjoint dynamics. In this work we study the related problem of deciding if the dynamics can be decomposed as the *synchronous* execution of smaller, independent dynamics. We formalise these two notions of composition of dynamics as the *sum* and *product* operations in the semiring of finite discrete-time dynamical systems (FDDSs or simply dynamical systems in the following).

The semiring of dynamical systems. Dynamical systems are pairs (X, f) where X is a finite set of states and $f: X \rightarrow X$ is a transition function; these are equivalent to functional digraphs, that is, with uniform outdegree 1. The set \mathbb{D} of dynamical systems *up to isomorphism* can be endowed with the structure of semiring [2] with two standard operations: the disjoint union $+$ and the direct product \times of the associated functional digraphs. More formally, given two dynamical systems (X, f) and (Y, g) we define $(X, f) + (Y, g) = (X \sqcup Y, f + g)$, where \sqcup is the disjoint union and

$$(f + g)(z) = \begin{cases} f(z) & \text{if } z \in X \\ g(z) & \text{if } z \in Y. \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, we set $(X, f) \times (Y, g) = (X \times Y, f \times g)$ where $(f \times g)(x, y) = (f(x), g(y))$. For instance, the product below represents the synchronous execution of the two dynamical systems on the left-hand side, all systems being taken up to isomorphism:

RSs as dynamical systems. We can interpret any RS $\mathcal{A} = (S, A)$ as a dynamical system over 2^S with transition function $\text{res}_{\mathcal{A}}: 2^S \rightarrow 2^S$. We will denote the pair $(2^S, \text{res}_{\mathcal{A}})$ as $D(\mathcal{A})$. Recall that, for any dynamical system (X, f) such that $X = 2^S$ for some finite set S , there exists an RS that induces that

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dynamics [4]. The sum operation $+$ is not closed for RSs, only being defined if the resulting dynamical system also has a power of 2 as its cardinality. On the other hand, the product \times has a straightforward meaning for RSs. Let $\mathcal{A} = (S_{\mathcal{A}}, A)$ and $\mathcal{B} = (S_{\mathcal{B}}, B)$ two RSs with disjoint background sets¹ ($S_{\mathcal{A}} \cap S_{\mathcal{B}} = \emptyset$); then, the union of their reactions gives an RS $\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B} = (S_{\mathcal{A}} \cup S_{\mathcal{B}}, A \cup B)$ whose associated dynamical system $D(\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{B})$ coincides with $D(\mathcal{A}) \times D(\mathcal{B})$.

If \mathcal{A} is given by the reactions $(\emptyset, \{\diamond, \heartsuit\}, \{\heartsuit\})$ and $(\{\heartsuit\}, \{\diamond\}, \{\diamond, \heartsuit\})$ over $S_{\mathcal{A}} = \{\diamond, \heartsuit\}$ and \mathcal{B} is given by the reaction $(\emptyset, \emptyset, \{\spadesuit\})$ over $S_{\mathcal{B}} = \{\spadesuit\}$, the dynamics of the union of these two RSs corresponds to the following product:

This is a concrete implementation (among many possible ones) of the abstract dynamics depicted in the previous example.

Irreducible dynamics. An open question in the semiring \mathbb{D} is finding an efficient algorithm to detect if a given dynamical system is *irreducible* (with respect to the product), or proving that the problem is intractable. In this work we analyse the same problem in the context of RSs, that is, on an exponentially succinct representation of the dynamics. We say that an RS $\mathcal{A} = (S, A)$ is *dynamically reducible* if there exists two dynamical systems D_1 and D_2 such that $D(\mathcal{A}) = D_1 \times D_2$. Since $|D_1|$ and $|D_2|$ must divide $|D(\mathcal{A})| = 2^{|S|}$, then D_1 and D_2 are themselves the dynamics of two RSs.

We can prove that, given an RS $\mathcal{A} = (S, A)$, deciding if \mathcal{A} is dynamically irreducible is an **NP**-hard problem. Furthermore, this hardness result holds even if we assume a constant bound on the number of entities per reaction: indeed, we can reduce 3SAT to the problem of detecting irreducibility for $\mathcal{RS}(3, 5)$, where reactions have at most 3 reactants and 5 inhibitors.

This shows that the problem is presumably intractable. However, a complexity upper bound is unknown, which could imply that an even stronger hardness result is possible. Furthermore, the complexity of the problem is open for more restricted resource-bounded RSs, such as inhibitorless or reactantless RSs, where it is also nontrivial to establish if the factor dynamics can themselves be generated by RSs having the same restrictions.

References

- [1] Rocco Ascone, Giulia Bernardini, and Luca Manzoni. Cycles and global attractors of reactantless and inhibitorless reaction systems. *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, 1045:115300, 2025.
- [2] Alberto Dennunzio, Valentina Dorigatti, Enrico Formenti, Luca Manzoni, and Antonio E. Porreca. Polynomial equations over finite, discrete-time dynamical systems. In *Cellular Automata, 13th International Conference on*

¹This construction can be generalised to non-disjoint background sets by renaming the entities (or, equivalently, by taking their disjoint union).

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- [3] Alberto Dennunzio, Enrico Formenti, Luca Manzoni, and Antonio E. Porreca. Complexity of the dynamics of reaction systems. *Inf. Comput.*, 267:96–109, 2019.
- [4] Andrzej Ehrenfeucht and Grzegorz Rozenberg. Reaction systems. *Fundam. Informaticae*, 75(1-4):263–280, 2007.
- [5] Daniela Genova, Hendrik Jan Hoogeboom, and Nataša Jonoska. A graph isomorphism condition and equivalence of reaction systems. *Theoretical Computer Science*, 701:109–119, 2017.